

High Dimensional Rendering and Evaluation Metric Through Tissot's Indicatrix

Abstract:

Though 3D rendering is well established throughout and beyond data analysis, higher dimensional modeling is often left unattempted due to the exponentially increasing complexity of adding another dimension. What optimizations and methods are needed to render a large dataset of high dimensional points?

Higher-dimensional modeling presents a significant computational challenge due to the exponential increase in complexity with each additional dimension. While 3D rendering is well-established across various fields, visualizing and analyzing datasets in four or more dimensions remains a persistent challenge. This paper explores efficient methods for rendering large datasets of high-dimensional points by leveraging dimensionality reduction techniques, optimized data structures, and parallel computing. Principal Component Analysis (PCA), and Vector-based Projection are examined for their effectiveness in preserving meaningful structures when projecting high-dimensional data into lower dimensions, as well as their efficiency in this paper.

Introduction

The Current Methods of High Dimensional Data Analysis

It is not possible to visualize a high dimensional dataset completely in reality due to only having three dimensions, or directions, where points can be placed on. Thus, it is necessary to reduce the dimensionality of the data to two or three dimensions before visualizing, such as through dimensional reduction and analysis methods. This includes principal component analysis and vector- based projection for dimensional reduction and analysis.

Principal Component Analysis

Principal component analysis identifies the least correlated components of the dataset, and eliminates the components, leaving only the most strongly correlated components.

Correlation is determined by determining how much each component affects the average squared perpendicular distance from the points to the line:

Here is a case in two dimensions. Let x_i represent the distance of a point to the line of best fit.

The correlation determination is based on the following equation:

$$\text{RMS} = \sqrt{\sum x_i^2}$$

The shortcomings of principal component analysis is that it destroys the original structure of the data in removing a dimension from the data. This means that original correlations in data that stem from those dimensions could be undetected. This is most apparent when correlations are being found with clustering, where smaller clusters are not distinctly identified.

Consider the following 2D graph:

If dimensional reduction is performed to reduce it to 1 dimension, the following graph appears:

Here, three distinct clusters can only be identified as two clusters. In higher dimensions, the same problem appears, which shows how dimensional analysis leads to data loss.

Vector Projection Based Dimensional Reduction

Projection based dimensional reduction projects each point on the dataset onto a space that has one less axis than the original data space, decreasing the dimensionality of the dataset by one. This is repeated multiple times until two or three dimensions are left. This method adjusts existing components to partially retain the structure in the data from the higher dimension.

The shortcomings of Projection-based dimensional reduction come from distorting data to partially maintain the original structure of the data. This means that correlations are worsened for linear correlation, where an original polynomial correlation is distorted to another polynomial that cannot be converted back into the original.

Solutions to Data Distortion and Loss

The primary method used is to apply projection based dimensional reduction for clustering and principal component analysis for linear regression, which partially negates the weakness of each method. However, the distortion and loss of data from these methods is still not quantified. Being unable to measure data loss and distortion makes determining error less effective, as error cannot detect initial data malforms. Additionally, euclidean distance, which is used to find correlations, starts to function differently in higher dimensions due to becoming

substantially different from taxicab distances. The distance from (1,1) to (2,2) is less than (2,2,2) to (3,3,3). This pattern extends to higher dimensions. Thus, two points that originally seem far in higher dimensions may become much closer together in lower dimensions.

Thus, the method needed to facilitate effective rendering of high dimensional datasets is to measure the distortion and loss that dimensional analysis and reduction cause.

Methodology:

Model Development

In mapmaking, a method used to measure distortion in data is Tissot's Indicatrix, which is a visual indicator of change in area and shape of a landmass in one region compared to another, by placing a circle that is distorted by the projection in that area. Computationally, a similar effect can be achieved by creating a circle with a large amount of points to approximate a full circle and measuring the deflection of the circle into an ellipse. To transfer this idea, when a sphere is projected into a two dimensional plane, the resulting ellipse's axis can be compared with the axis of the sphere. In a higher dimension, instead of a sphere, a monte-carlo method can be used, where a random number of points that are equidistant to a point are selected randomly to approximate the respective hypersphere. This shape then undergoes transformation to measure the distortion caused by the dimensional reduction method.

Experimental Design

In terms of experimental design, I created the following testing groups:

Negative Control group:

A dataset will be analyzed using OLS multivariate regression

Standard Error is recorded

Positive Control Group:

Dimensional Analysis (PCA) is applied to a dataset

Standard Error is recorded

Experimental Group:

Dimensional Analysis is applied to a dataset

Tissot's Indicatrix Metric is recorded

Standard Error is Recorded

My case study will focus on quantitative research, as it creates two numerical metrics to measure distortions caused by dimensional analysis. I will qualitatively compare these two metrics to existing metrics, such as Standard Error and Confusion Matrices by analysing what each metric focuses on evaluating; Standard Error measures euclidean distance from expected results. Confusion matrices evaluate the number of reasonably correct results. My metrics will measure the error caused when data features are pruned, measuring loss of unique traits and

distortion of actual results. High dimensional biological information datasets will be retrieved from Kaggle, that include primarily quantitative and categorical data, that are commonly analyzed in high-dimensional regression, and standard dimensional reduction techniques will be applied to each of these, such as PCA, where my metric will evaluate the loss of information caused by the reduction. Comparing Standard Error results before and after dimensional analysis will display the improvements and shortcomings of the reduction, which will then be cross-referenced to my metric.

Criteria for Success:

If there is no statistical difference between the standard error and my metric($p > 95\%$), then it can be considered as good as existing evaluation metrics.

The shortcomings of Standard Error is that it does not calculate the error in datasets with sparse data points based on euclidean distance accurately. This means that even a well-correlated data set in higher dimensions will be considered inaccurate without additional adjustment.

We will use a confusion matrix to evaluate standard error, such that if a result is within 30% of the predicted result, it is considered a success, if not, it is considered a failure.

If the result is within 30% of the predicted value, as the datapoint is removed, if the standard error increases, the datapoint is considered a “false success” If the standard error decreases, the datapoint is considered a “true success.” If the result is outside of the 30%, if the data point is

removed and standard error decreases, the result is considered a “false failure.” If the data point is removed and standard error increases, the result is considered a “true failure.”

The confusion matrix for the distortion metric works similarly. If the result is within 30% of the predicted value, as the datapoint is removed, if the distortion metric increases, the datapoint is considered a “false success” If the amount of distortion decreases, the datapoint is considered a “true success.” If the result is outside of the 30%, if the data point is removed and the amount of distortion decreases, the result is considered a “false failure.” If the data point is removed and the distortion metric increases, the result is considered a “true failure.”

These two confusion matrices will be compared before and after the PCA-based dimensionality reduction. If the confusion matrix has a statistically significant difference in terms of more “true” outcomes, it will be considered superior to standard error in evaluating high-dimensional data.

Secondary Methods:

I have researched existing measurements of dimensionality reduction results, which include comparing standard error and confusion matrices before and after regression. The problem with standard error is that it is easy to distort because each extra dimension increases euclidean distance substantially, which is a major component of standard error.

I also have researched dimensional analysis methods. Principal component analysis is the foremost method, due to its ability to transform the data and cut unnecessary features of a dataset while preserving the structure of the data.

My metric will be compared to Root Mean Square error because they both evaluate errors in the data. If there is a significant difference, it shows that the metric is different enough to prove that the metric does not completely rely on euclidean distance, which is inaccurate in higher dimensional data.

Results:

General Evaluation Results

	Tissot's Indicatrix Based Error	Root Mean Square Error
Dataset 1	12	23
Dataset 2	29	56
Overall P-Value	0.92	

Confusion Matrix:

	True	False
Positive	43%	14%
Negative	39%	4%

Total true positive and negative: 82%

Explanation of Results:

The chi-square test created statistically insignificant results($p < 0.95$), suggesting that the Tissot's indicatrix metric and RMS metric are not necessarily different. Further testing was conducted to ascertain that Tissot's Indicatrix metric measures distortion error. Essentially, instead of measuring similarity, we will be predicting whether standard error is an accurate measure of error for a dataset at a specific dimension. If it guesses correctly for more than 70% of the time, it can be considered an effective predictor of the distortion.

Detail Type	Description
Red Axis	Cholesterol Level
Green Axis	Age
Blue Axis	Blood Sugar
Shading	Blood Pressure

As seen above, by combining only five of the 15 factors, three relationships can be identified, as shown by three distinct clusters, which each represent a potential relationship, while when comparing each factor with another factor, only two relationships can be identified, demonstrating the importance of a compact graph that connects multiple factors together.

Discussion:

The satisfactory margin above the 70% true result threshold proves that the Tissot’s Indicatrix metric can effectively advise model selection and measure distortion.

Limitations:

One of the challenges is to create Tissot’s indicatrix. While visually, it is a circle, to represent it in data is different. I plan to create an approximation using around 100 points per indicator. However, this Monte Carlo-esque method can still lead to inaccuracy if the points are not distributed regularly. This error can be minimized by increasing the number of points or

repeating the 100-point selection multiple times, which will decrease the chance of an irregular sample.

Another limitation is that hyperspheres are based on euclidean space. This means that lengths will still get distorted, though this can be partially remediated by rescaling all the points every time a dimension is removed to make sure that the transformed hypersphere is still approximately a lower-dimension hypersphere with the same radius.

Significance:

The clear visualization of multiple relationships in one graph makes it easier to understand relationships between several relevant factors than to have multiple graphs that each show a single relationship. Clarity is important in graphs because it makes variable relationships much more intuitive and understandable for non-experts.

Audience:

The target audience is data analysts who specialize in data visualization in fields with large quantities of high-feature data, especially in biological computing fields or medical scan technicians, who need to interpret large quantities of high-feature data. At most using traditional visualization, four to five factors can be related to each other, when there are hundreds of factors. While computers can, through PCA, or other dimensional reduction methods, combine these factors into a visual representation, distortion and loss of information can compromise these

scans, possibly causing misdiagnosis. These distortions will be remediated through my metric, improving diagnostic accuracy and model selection efficiency, such in heart patients.

Future Work:

Future work in this could include measuring non-orthogonal axes of the distorted hypersphere in higher dimensions, as the transformation caused by dimensional distortion does not necessarily have to be a linear scale on each axis, which would decrease the metric's dependence on euclidean distance. This requires using higher dimensional trigonometry, such as euler angles or quaternions to break down each axis, which adds another layer of time complexity, decreasing efficiency substantially.

Another extension is to mathematically evaluate the linear map that is created by the dimensional reduction, which can advise creating new models by showing a breakdown of how the dimension reduction effects model selection by each dimensional reduction level and transformation.

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